

E-COMMERCE BUSINESS FOR

BUDDING

ENTREPRENEURS

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EVOLUTION OF

E-COMMERCE

Launch of Online B2B (matrimonial) portal

Launch of online travel agents and entry of a E-tailing segment

1995

1996

1997

2006-2007

2010

Launch of Internet In India Via Dialup

Launch of Online job portal

Launch of first group buying website in India

WAYS OF SELLING PRODUCTS ONLINE

SOCIAL MEDIA

MARKET PLACE

OWN WEBSITES

PROS AND CONS

Selling on Online Marketplaces vs. Selling on own website

Marketplaces

★Pros★

1. Lots of traffic potential.
2. Little Tech knowledge is needed.

★Cons★

1. Commission Fee charged.
2. Little or no Branding control.

Website

★Pros★

1. Complete control of brand image .
2. Control over customization.

★Cons★

1. Proactive Marketing is needed
2. More technical involvement.

E-COM

PROCESS

1. RECEIVE

2. SORT

3. STORE

4. ORDER PLACED

5. PACK

6. LABELED

DOCUMENTS

REQUIRED
G GST

PAN Card P

B Bank Account

Name N

APPROVELS TO BE

REQUIRED

To Sell Branded Products

Brand Approvals from The Brand

To Sell our Own Brand Products

Trade Mark Registration Certificate

To Sell General Products

GTIN (Global Trade Item Number) Exemption Certificate

CHOOSE YOUR PRODUCT TO SELL

INVESTMENT AND

STOCK

₹10,000-₹15,000

Own Cash or Borrowed

Minimum 10 with GST bill

PRODUCT WEB SOURCES

FACILITIES NEEDED

Internet

Laptop

Mobile

TAB

Desktop

PC

CHOOSE YOUR CUSTOMERS

1. Define the ideal customer for what you sell. ...
2. Determine the specific benefits your customer is seeking in buying your product. ...
3. Determine the location of your exact customer. ...
4. Determine exactly when your ideal customer buys your product or service. ...
5. Determine your customer's buying strategy.

PHOTOGRAPHY OF YOUR PRODUCT

GST RETURN FILING

1

Download Sales Report
from E-commerce
Website

2

Split the Sales Returns in
to two
1.Sales Data
2.Credit Note/
Goods Returned

3

Upload the Excel File on
Clear Tax

MISCELLANEOUS

FACTORS TO BE CONSIDER WHILE

PRICING

MARKETING

151

PACKAGING

BEWARE RETURNS

1. **Incorrect Product or Size Ordered. ...**
2. **Product No Longer Needed. ...**
3. **Product Does Not Match Description on Website ...**
4. **Product Did Not Meet Customer's Expectations. ...**
5. **Company Shipped Wrong Product or Size. ...**
6. **Customer Unfamiliar with Retail Interface. ...**
7. **Customer Unfamiliar with Product.**

3rd PARTY REGISTRATION GATEWAYS

amazon seller central India

Create Account

Your name

Mobile number

IN +91 Mobile number

Email (optional)

Password

At least 6 characters

i Passwords must be at least 6 characters.

We will send you a text to verify your phone. Message and Data rates may apply.

Continue

Flipkart Seller Hub

Create your Seller Account

+91 - Enter Your Mobile Number

Enter Your Email Address

Enter Your Full Name

By filling this form, I agree to [Terms of Use](#)

SIGN UP

Already a Seller? [Login Here](#)

ebay

Personal Business

Email

Reenter email

Password

First name Last name

- +91 Mobile phone

By Registering, you agree that you've read and accepted our [User Agreement](#), you're at least 18 years old, and you consent to our [Privacy Notice](#) and receiving marketing communications from us.

Register

REGISTERING IN

→ ↻ 🏠 sellercentral.amazon.in/sw/in/INSSR/step/SignUp?passthrough%2Faccount=soa&passthrough%2FsuperSource=OAR&ref_=sdin_soa_hp&passthrough%2Fm

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amazon seller central
India

Register and Start Selling

Please have the following ready before you begin:

- Your bank account details for receiving payments from Amazon
- Tax (GST/PAN) details of your business

Please ensure that all the information you submit is accurate.

Enter details below to continue registration

Company/Business name ⓘ

Enter the company/business name as registered in GST/PAN

Seller Agreement

I have read and agree to comply with and/or be bound by the terms and conditions of [Amazon Services Business Solutions Agreement](#) , [Easy Ship Service & Runway Terms and Conditions](#) and [Amazon Business \(B2B\) Terms & Conditions](#)

Continue

Like to create new account? [Click here](#)

SELLER INFORMATION

sellercentral.amazon.in/sw/in/SignUp/step/Seller+Information?productTier=SILVER&productType=SellOnAmazon&mons_sel_locale=en_IN

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Phone Verification Seller Information Tax Details Dashboard

Tell us about your business

Store Name ⓘ
ssk_ssk [Check Availability](#)
✔ Store Name is available.

Select Product Category ⓘ
Furniture ▼

Enter your address ⓘ

407 A , Kamaraj Nagar,, CHIDAMBARAM, TAMIL NADU, 608602, IN
[View all saved addresses](#)

Add a new address

[Continue](#)

FAQ

- Can I change Store Name?
- Can I change the category later?
- Which address should I enter?
- What products are not supported by Amazon?
- My Address is not eligible for Amazon Easy Ship, what should I do?
- Can I enter multiple pickup addresses?

Help Center

2STEP VERIFICATION

sellercentral.amazon.in/a/settings/approval/setup/register?hide_breadcrumb=true&hide_nav_menu=true&logo_id=amzn_sc&return_to=%2Fsw%2Fin%2FLau... ☆

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amazon seller central

Step 1 of 2

Enroll a 2SV authenticator

Phone number Use your phone as a 2SV authenticator

Tell us the mobile number that you would like to use as your authenticator. When you sign in, we will send this number a text message with a one time password.

Enter your mobile number

IN +91 ▾

8903645630

Receive One Time Password (OTP) by:

- Text message (SMS)
- Voice delivery--you will receive an automated phone call.

Continue

Message and data rates may apply.

Authenticator App Generate OTP using an application. No network connectivity required.

DEVICE SIGN-IN

METHOD

Step 2 of 2

Almost done...

Just two more important things to know:

1. Legacy device Sign-In method

Some devices are unable to display a second screen prompting you to enter the OTP, but Two-Step Verification will still be required. Here's how it will work:

- 1. Sign in with your password. An error message will occur.
- 2. An OTP will be sent to your preferred phone. You may also use an authenticator app.
- 3. Add ("append") the OTP to the end of your password, and click "Sign-In" again.

TAX DETAILS

sellercentral.amazon.in/sw/in/Launch/step/Tax+Details?alertId=enable-succeeded

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Phone Verification Seller Information Tax Details Dashboard

Update your Tax details

I have GSTIN number

Enter your tax details

TAMIL NADU

Seller Legal Name [What's this?](#)
SSK

GST Number [What's this?](#)

PAN number [What's this?](#)

I will Update Later

I want to only sell in GST exempt category like books.

FAQ

- Which PAN should I enter?
- What is Seller Legal Name?
- Why is my PAN/GSTIN non-editable?

DASHBOARD

sellercentral.amazon.in/sw/in/Launch/step/Dashboard?alertId=enable-succeeded

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central India English

Phone Verification Seller Information Tax Details Dashboard

Hi ssk_ssk,
Please complete the below steps and start selling to millions of customer

Products to sell

List the products you wish to sell on Amazon.in

Start selling in these categories:
Furniture

Start Listing

Learn how to list your products

How to list your products?

FEE

DASHBOARD...

sellercentral.amazon.in/sw/in/Launch/step/Dashboard?alertId=enable-succeeded

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[Learn more about Amazon's charges](#)

Request paid professional help with product photos or listings

- Shipping Fee Details
- Bank Account Details
- Enter Tax Details
- Default Product Tax Code
- Signature

Launch your business

[Continue to Seller Central](#)

OUR HOME PAGE

sellercentral.amazon.in/home

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Catalogue Inventory Pricing Orders Advertising Growth Reports Performance Appstore Services B2B

MARKETPLACES 1	ORDERS 0	TODAY'S SALES ₹0.00	BUYER MESSAGES 0	BUY BOX WINS --	ACCOUNT HEALTH	CUSTOMER FEEDBACK ☆☆☆☆☆ (0)
TOTAL BALANCE ₹0.00	GLOBAL PROMOTIONS SALES --					

News

JUL 22, 2021
Payment Service Provider Programme update
[Read more >](#)

JUL 16, 2021
Are you ready for Prime Day on 26 July 2021 and 27 July 2021?
[Read more >](#)

JUL 15, 2021
Update to Sell Software Policy
[Read more >](#)

[FEEDBACK](#) X

Deposit Method

Your deposit method is missing or invalid

A valid deposit method is required to use your Selling on Amazon account and receive disbursements.

[Add or update deposit method](#)

Action needed

Action needed: Update your emergency contact number

In the instance a critical event occurs that affects your ability to sell, we may try to contact you. Help us reach you by ensuring that your emergency phone number is accurate.

[Update now](#)

Seller Forums

JUL 23, 2021
Customer unable to place order
[Read more >](#)

LISTING OF PRODUCTS IN

Step 1

LISTING OF PRODUCTS IN AMAZON

Add a Product

[Selling application status](#)

[Show tour](#)

List a new product

Search Amazon's catalog first

If it is not in Amazon's catalog: [Create a new product listing](#)

List many products via bulk upload

Use Inventory File Templates

[Download an Inventory File](#)

[Check and Upload your Inventory File](#)

[Monitor Upload Status](#)

Or

Step 2

LISTING OF PRODUCTS IN AMAZON

Create a new product: Classify

To start creating a detail page, first classify your product. [Learn more](#)

Search for your product's category

The product you are adding may already exist on Amazon:

1
CLASSIFY

Step 3

LISTING OF PRODUCTS IN

AMAZON

Browse for your product's category

Note: If you do not see your product's category listed below, it may require approval, as the category for your application is under review. [Learn more](#) or check your [selling application status](#).

All Product Categories

- Apparel ▶
- Appliances ▶
- Arts, Crafts & Sewing ▶
- Automotive ▶
- Baby Products ▶
- Beauty ▶
- Books ▶
- Camera & Photo ▶
- Cell Phone Accessories ▶
- Computer & Video Games ▶
- Computers ▶
- Electronics ▶
- Everything Else ▶
- Health & Personal Care ▶
- Home & Garden ▶
- Industrial & Scientific ▶

Step 4

LISTING OF PRODUCTS IN AMAZON

All categories with: **water bottle**

1 to 12 of 13 Possible Categories

Refine Your Search

[Baby Products](#) (1)
[Home & Garden](#) (6)
[Pet Supplies](#) (1)
[Sporting Goods](#) (3)
[Toys & Games](#) (1)

Categories

[Bike Water Bottle Cages](#)

Found In: Sporting Goods > Cycling > Cycling Equipment > Bike Accessories

[Other Baby Bottle Supplies](#)

Found In: Baby Products > Feeding > Baby Bottle Supplies

[Sports Water Bottle Accessories](#)

Found In: Sporting Goods > General Sporting Goods > General Sporting Equipment

[Sports Water Bottles](#)

Found In: Sporting Goods > General Sporting Goods > General Sporting Equipment

[Bottle Openers](#)

Found In: Home & Garden > Kitchen > Barware

[Wine Bottle Stoppers](#)

Found In: Home & Garden > Kitchen > Barware > Wine Accessories

[Other Swimming Pool & Outdoor Water Toys](#)

Found In: Toys & Games > Swimming & Pools > Swimming Pool & Outdoor Water Toys

[Commercial Bottle Coolers](#)

Found In: Home & Garden > Kitchen > Food Service > Food Service Equipment

[Other Barware](#)

Found In: Home & Garden > Kitchen > Barware

[Disposable Bottle Carriers](#)

Found In: Home & Garden > Kitchen > Food Service

[Replacement Kitchen Countertop Water Filters](#)

Found In: Home & Garden > Cleaning Laundry & Organization > Water Filters > Replacement Water Filters

[Pet Water Bottles](#)

Found In: Pet Supplies > Pet Food & Feeding Supplies

Step 5

USE YOUR MOBILE AS COMPUTER

Hands on session

amazon

Flipkart

THANKS

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